

ASSESSMENT OF THE BIOTECHNOLOGICAL POTENTIAL OF XYLOTROPHIC FUNGI DISTRIBUTED IN AZERBAIJAN AS PRODUCERS OF POLYSACCHARIDES

Muradov P.Z¹., Bakhshaliyeva K.F¹⁻²., Aliyeva B.N¹., Garayeva S.J¹., Tomuyeva G.A³., Agayeva Z.T⁴., Khonagova Sh.B⁵., Namazov N.R⁶.

¹Institute of Microbiology of the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Baku(mpanah@mail.ru);

²Institute of Fruit and Tea Cultivation of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Guba;

³Institute of Bioresources, Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ganja city;

⁴Baku State University, Azerbaijan, Baku c.;

⁵Azerbaijan State University of Economics (UNEC), Baku c.;

⁶Sumgait State Universiteti, AR, Sumgait c.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17185075>

Abstract. *In the conducted studies, the species composition of xylotrophic macromycetes distributed in various forests of the Republic of Azerbaijan was determined and a collection of cultures isolated from them was created. 225 cultures from 75 species included in the collection were screened for total biomass and polysaccharide content. It was clear that the cultures tested differed from each other in terms of both total biomass and the amount of polysaccharides contained in the biomass. It was determined that strains belonging to the genera Ganoderma, Pleurotus, Schizophyllum and others have higher indicators in terms of the total amount of polysaccharides, and it was determined that it is promising to obtain preparations with different activities and effects from them.*

Keywords: *forest ecosystem, xylotrophic macromycetes, polysaccharides, biological activity.*

Currently, the cultivation of mushrooms for biomass production is the most suitable and affordable way to obtain products that are safe and have a wide range of effects (antitumor, antibacterial, antiviral, antioxidant, immunostimulating, laxative, stimulating, inhibiting, etc.) in most regions of the world [2, 10]. Thus, this approach attracts attention both in terms of the utilization of waste generated in various fields, primarily in the agricultural sector, and due to the high labor, it also opens wide prospects for the creation of new jobs for people. For this reason, mushroom production has been developing rapidly in recent years, both in quantitative and qualitative terms. The fact that fungi, which are characterized by great diversity, are active producers of metabolites that are useful for various (food, feed, medical and technical) purposes [8, 12] necessitates the development of more products from them. The number of mushroom species currently used for one purpose or another is far greater than the number of species known to science. It would be appropriate to note one fact about this. Currently, the number of edible mushrooms intensively cultivated for food purposes is slightly over 30 [5], although the number of mushrooms belonging to this category is 10 times greater. For this reason, expanding both the number of species of mushrooms used as a source of products suitable for food purposes and the

assortment of products obtained from them is one of the directions of modern research. The relevance of this issue attracts attention for another reason. Thus, the natural soil-climate and plant world of a given region are different, and due to their influence, the biological activity of fungi spreading in those areas and the amount of biomass they produce in natural conditions are characterized by different quantitative indicators. This also allows us to note that there is a high probability of the spread of strains of fungi with higher productivity compared to known strains in different regions, and this probability is also high. The reason for such a high probability is that the study of such fungi today is not complete enough, and mycological studies have either not been conducted, or those conducted in the past did not cover sufficient cenoses.

Against the background of the above, if we evaluate the situation in the Republic of Azerbaijan, which has a rich and diverse nature and a wide variety of soil and climatic conditions, it becomes clear that the situation here is not at a level that can be assessed as unequivocally positive. All of these are issues that stand out for their relevance in the comprehensive study of xylotrophic macromycetes distributed in the nature of Azerbaijan, primarily in terms of their species composition and the ecological and biotechnological foundations of their use for the purpose of obtaining food products. Therefore, the presented work is directed to the solution of these issues.

For the research, natural forests located in various areas of the Republic of Azerbaijan (Guba-Khasmaz, Sheki-Zagatala, Karabakh, East Zangezur and other economic regions) were selected as the main area and their xylomycobiota was comprehensively evaluated for its species composition and biotechnological potential as a producer of biologically active substances, primarily polysaccharides.

The collection of fruiting bodies of the fungus, whose distribution was determined on this or that tree, their on-site passporting, their initial identification, the isolation of pure cultures in the laboratory, and the final determination of the species composition were carried out in accordance with the classical methods and approaches accepted in mycology [1, 3-4, 6, 9], as well as those used in our own work [7]. The biomass yield and polysaccharide content of mushrooms extracted from pure cultures were also evaluated based on known methods and approaches.

At the initial stage of the research, the forests located in the studied areas were studied for the species composition of xylotrophic macromycetes, and during the research period, it was determined that 75 species (225 strains) of xylotrophic macromycetes participated in the formation of the mycobiota of these forests. Based on the results obtained, it was determined that the fungi whose distribution was recorded are characterized by a wide diversity according to the main indicators (occurrence frequency - OF, ecotrophic relationships, distribution on different substrates, biochemical composition of biomass yield, toxicity, etc.). Despite this, studies have shown that there are species among fungi that are promising perspective in terms of their main indicators under natural conditions, that some of them are even dominant in terms of OF, and that the biotrophy or saprotrophy of most of them is not a true character (i.e. polytropy) are data determined in the studies conducted. This information is essential when using mushrooms for various purposes, especially for food.

It should be noted that although the synthetic preparation of pharmaceuticals, various foods, and food additives led to great successes in the past, in recent times the expansion of both fundamental and practical research aimed at obtaining these from natural sources has become particularly important. In this regard, it is of particular importance that fungi are among the objects of attention. Thus, the worsening of the environmental situation, the gradual reduction of

forest area, and the increasing of anthropogenic impact on the environment are also leading to a decrease in traditionally used bioresources, including natural resources of mushrooms. In this regard, it is important to develop methods and approaches for more efficient use of natural resources and their use in accordance with their existing quantity in nature, as well as to correctly determine and predict the amount of bioresources formed in natural conditions.

Considering that the amount of fruiting bodies formed by fungi under natural conditions is limited and is only available during certain periods of the year (summer and autumn), the possibility of overcoming this limitation by using the biomass of these fungi in the vegetative growth phase has also been investigated. It has become clear that biologically active metabolites are also found in the biomass produced by fungi, both in natural conditions and during the vegetative growth phase. The fact that these metabolites do not have a toxic effect on plants or invertebrates (infusoria) such as *Tetrahymena pyriformis* and that they have a positive effect on the processes being tested has allowed us to note the possibility of solving the problem. It has become clear that fungi belonging to genera such as *Ganoderma* (3 strains), *Laetiporus* (1 strain), *Pleurotus* (3 strains), *Schizophyllum* (2 strains), *Trametes* (4 strains) and others (5 strains) are characterized by relatively high indicators in terms of biomass yield, which promises broad prospects for obtaining biopreparations for various purposes from them. In order to increase the quantitative indicator of the obtained biomass, the nutrient media used for their cultivation were optimized according to both their traditional parameters (carbon and nitrogen source, cultivation temperature, initial pH, etc.) and new parameters (low-frequency light waves, ultrasound, living sines extracts, use of various stimulants, etc.), and a slight increase in biomass yield (15-40%) was achieved. As a result of biochemical analysis of the obtained biomass, it became clear that the content of polysaccharides in their composition varies between 60.5-68.4%, the content of proteins 20.2-24.3%, the content of nucleic acids 0.62-0.87%, the content of lipids 2.1-3.2%, and the content of ash between 1.2-1.6%. It was also determined that the polysaccharides in the biomass of the mushroom cultures selected as active producers consisted of insoluble and soluble fractions and their ratio was approximately 12:1 in all strains. In addition, when determining the bonds in polysaccharide fractions, it became clear that the polysaccharides synthesized by some producers (especially *Ganoderma lucidum* S-76) contained a relatively high amount of 1,3- β -glucosidic bonds. This fact allows us to note the promising potential for obtaining pharmacologically active preparations from fungi selected as active producers.

Thus, in the conducted studies, a collection of cultures belonging to xylophilic macromycetes distributed in various areas of the Republic of Azerbaijan was created, and the polysaccharides synthesized by them were evaluated in terms of both quantity and composition. It has also been determined that among the cultures included in the collection, there are also those that have promising potential for use as active producers of substances with biological, including pharmacological, activity for biotechnological purposes.

LITERATURE

1. Arefev S.P. System analysis of the biota of wood-destroying fungi / S.P. Arefev, - Novosibirsk: Science, -2010, p-260
2. Barshteyn V.Y. Bioconversion of waste from the agro-industrial complex: monograph. - Novosibirsk: Publishing house ANS «SibAK», -2016.p -88.
3. Bondartseva M.A. Identification of mushrooms of Russia. Order Aphyllophoraceae. M.A. Bondartseva, / SPb.: Nauka, -1998, issue. 2, p-391.

4. Methods of experimental mycology/Ed. By Bilay V.Ī. -Kiev: “Naukova dumka”, -1982, -500p.
5. Minakov D.V. The influence of ecological and biochemical parameters of bioconversion of plant raw materials on the yield of biomass of fruiting bodies of xylotrophic basidiomycetes: /Abstract of dissertations of candidate of biological sciences /-Biysk, 2018, -25 p., 2018, -25 p.
6. Mukhin V. A. Field guide to tinder fungi / V. A. Mukhin –Ekaterinburg: - 1997, -104 p.
7. Bakhshaliyeva K., Namazov N., Hasanova A. et al. Assessment of the prospects of studying and using mushrooms of Azerbaijan as effective producers of biologically active substances// Periódico tchê química (Brazilia), - 2020, -v.17, № 34, -p.403-411.
8. Bell V, Silva C.R.P.G., Guina J., Fernandes T.H. Mushrooms as future generation healthy foods// Front Nutr., 2022 Dec 6;9:1050099. doi: 10.3389/fnut.2022.1050099.
9. Maheshwari R. Fungi:Experimental Methods In Biology, 2th Edition. CRC Pres, 2016, 358p.
10. Muszyńska B., Grzywacz-Kisielewska A., Kała K. et al. Anti-inflammatory properties of edible mushrooms (a review)./ B.Muszyńska, //Food Chem, -2017, -v.243, -p.373–381
11. Pouris J., Kolyva F., Bratakou, S. et al. The Role of Fungi in Food Production and Processing//Applied Sciences, 2024, 14(12), 5046. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14125046>
12. Sharma A., Aggarwal N.K., Yadav A. Isolation and Screening of Lignolytic Fungi from Various Ecological Niches.//Universal Journal of Microbiology Research, -2017, -v.5, -p.25-34.